

Julian Romance

also known as “Romance of Emperor Julian”, “Romance of Julian the Apostate”

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Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Ancient Novel, Christian Traditions, Hagiography, Text, Religious Group, Early Christianity, Apocalyptic Literature

The anonymous Christian Syriac work chronicling the life of Emperor Julian (d. 363 CE), known as Julian the Apostate for his attempt to revive traditional Roman religious practices in the final years of the Constantinian Dynasty. The Julian Romance is the apogee of a Late Antique tradition of Christian works antagonistic to Emperor Julian such as the Hymns against Julian of Ephrem Syrus and Orations 4 and 5 of Gregory of Nazianzus. While its extant recensions date back to at least the sixth century CE, the work potentially incorporates sources near contemporary to Julian’s reign. The text is likely an original Syriac composition and survives most extensively in ms. London, British Library Add. 14641 and ms. Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale Syr. 378. An early Arabic translation also survives in ms. Arabic 516 at St. Catherine’s Monastery in Mt. Sinai, Egypt. The genre of the work remains a matter of debate among scholars. Nineteenth-century German orientalist Theodor Nöldeke was the first western academic to publish a study of its extant manuscripts and to render its title as roman. Scholars in the later twentieth century such as M. van Esbroeck and J. H. Drijvers, however, have defined it as a work of hagiography and religious propaganda respectively. Itself a composite text and consisting of three main sections, the work covers: the ascension and apostasy of Julian; his persecution of the Christians, especially of Eusebius, the bishop of Rome; his eastern campaigns against Shapur II; his the divinely incurred and miraculous death; and the ascension of Jovian and his restoration of the Christian Empire. Although apocryphal, the Julian Romance was the most popular and influential account of the life of Emperor Julian in semitic literatures throughout Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages. Scholars such as G. J. Reinink have demonstrated the influence of the work on Syriac apocalyptic texts, especially the Apocalypse of Pseudo-Methodius. Accounts of the life of Julian drawn from the Julian Romance also appear in a number of Arabic universal chronicles including al-Ṭabarī, Agapius of Hieropolis, al-Mas‘ūdī, and Ibn al-Athīr.

Date Range: 361 CE - 599 CE

Region: Edessa

Region tags: Edessa

Edessa was an ancient Greek polis founded in the upper Mesopotamian. It became an important city in the Roman-Persian frontier during Late Antiquity.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Sokoloff, Michael. 2016. *The Julian Romance: A New English Translation*. Piscataway, NJ: Gorgias Press.

– Source 2: Nöldeke, Theodor. 1874. “Über den syrischen Roman von Kaiser Julian” in Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft 28.2/3, pp. 263-292.

– Source 3: Muraviev, Alexei. 1999. “The Syriac Julian Romance and Its Place in the Literary History” in Khristianskij Vostok 1, pp. 194-206.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://gedsh.bethmardutho.org/Julian-Romance>

– Source 1 Description: Gorgias Encyclopedic Dictionary of the Syriac Heritage: Electronic Edition

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/selectionfromsy00juli>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Inked

– with Ink

Notes: Refers to British Library ms. London, British Library Add. 14641

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Vellum

Notes: Refers to British Library ms. London, British Library Add. 14641

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery
– No

↳ Temple
– No

↳ Shrine
– No

↳ Altar
– No

↳ Devotional marker
– No

↳ Cenotaph
– No

↳ Church
– No

↳ Mosque
– No

↳ Synagogue
– No

↳ Triumphal Arch
– No

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↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Refers to British Library ms. London, British Library Add. 14641

↳ Specify

– Specify: See Wright, W. 1987. *Catalogue of The Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum Acquired Since the Year 1838*. Longmans & Co.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Syriac became the primary literary language of Christian communities throughout the Near East from the 4th to 8th c. CE. However, it remains a liturgical language of Eastern Christianity to this day.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: The text is written in Syriac, a dialect of Aramaic and a liturgical and literary language used among Christian communities most prominently before the 4th and 8th c. CE.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Institutions

Notes: It remains the liturgical language of Syriac Christianity to this day.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– No

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

–Other [specify]: See notes

Notes: The text deals with the end of the Constantinian Dynasty, which (according to the text) was destroyed by the misdeeds of Julian. However, the text also emphasizes the revitalization of the Roman Christian polity under his successor, Jovian.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The hand of God is often described as influencing or guiding events such as the failed attempts on Bishop Eusebius' life and Julian's own death in battle.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: N/A

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - No
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - No
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - No
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - No
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - No
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
 - I don't know
- ↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
 - No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: N/A

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– No

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: N/A

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Julian's death due to his rejection and persecution of Christianity is presaged throughout the text and is a prominent theme of the work.

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

↳ Sickness or illness?

– Yes

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: N/A

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: N/A

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: See Reinink, G. J. 1992. "The Romance of Julian the Apostate as a source for seventh century Syriac Apocalypses" in *La Syrie de Byzance à l'Islam*. eds. P. Canivet & J.-P. Rey-Coquais. Institut français de Damas, pp. 75-86.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– I don't know

↳ At specified time in future

– I don't know

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– I don't know

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– I don't know

↳ At some other time [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– I don't know

↳ Divine judgment event

– I don't know

- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - I don't know
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - I don't know
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: N/A
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?
 - I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– I don't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– I don't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– I don't know

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– I don't know

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– I don't know

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A city-state

Notes: Text is closely identified with the polis of Edessa.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– I don't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: The text deals in part with the expatriation of the Nisibis of its Christian community following its loss to the Persian Empire following the death the Julian.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Han Drijvers. *The Syriac Julian Romance: Aspects of the Jewish-Christian Controversy in Late Antiquity*.

Reference: W. Wright. *Catalogue of The Syriac Manuscripts in the British Museum Acquired Since the Year 1838*. Longmans & Co.

Reference: Abed El-Rahman Tayyara. *The Evolution of the Story of Julian the Apostate in Early Islamic Sources*.

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Reference: Alexei Muraviev. *The Syriac Julian Romance and Its Place in the Literary History*.

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